

101136318 – SUSTAIN-HTA
Support Utilisation of Sustainable and
TAilored INnovative methods for HTA

D1.8 – Second Yearly Overview of HTA Methods

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V1.0	9 March 2026	Draft for Steering Committee Review
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DEFINITIONS

Partners of the SUSTAIN-HTA Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

1. **UU** Universiteit Utrecht (Netherlands)
2. **UB** Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi (Italy)
3. **EMC** Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam (Netherlands)
4. **ZIN** Zorginstituut Nederland (Netherlands)
5. **RUMC** Stichting Radboud Universitair Medisch Centrum (Netherlands)
6. **SRI** Syreon Kutato Intezet Korlatolt Felelossegu Tarsasag (Hungary)
7. **OSTEBA** Fundacion Vasca de Innovacion e Investigacion Sanitarias (Spain)
8. **GetReal I** GetReal Institute (Netherlands)
9. **SYNAPSE** Synapse Research Management Partners (Spain)
10. **NIPN** Nemzeti Nepegészségügyi és Gyógyszerészeti Központ (Hungary)
11. **AGE.NA.S** Agenzia Nazionale per i Servizi Sanitari Regionali (Italy)
12. **AQUAS** Agencia de Qualitat i Avaluació Sanitaries de Catalunya (Spain)
13. **NOMA** Statens Legemiddelverk (Norway)
14. **UCSC** Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (Italy)
15. **NICE** National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (United Kingdom)

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency for the undertaking of the SUSTAIN-HTA project (101136318).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The SUSTAIN-HTA Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst SUSTAIN-HTA partners for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EU	European Union
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
HTACG	Member State Coordination Group on Health Technology Assessment
HTAi	Health Technology Assessment International
IHI	Innovative Health Initiative
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
ISPOR	International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research
RWD	Real-World Data
RWE	Real-World Evidence
SMDM	Society for Medical Decision Making
SUSTAIN-OBS	SUSTAIN Methods Observatory Tool
SUSTAIN-HS	SUSTAIN Horizon Scanning Tool

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the second annual overview of HTA methods undertaken within the SUSTAIN-HTA Coordination and Support Action and documents the continued development of the SUSTAIN Methods Observatory Tool (SUSTAIN-OBS). The observatory addresses a persistent challenge in health technology assessment (HTA): despite substantial investment in methodological research, particularly by the EU, the resulting methods, tools, and frameworks are often scattered across reports and publications, making them difficult to locate and constraining their uptake in routine HTA practice. SUSTAIN-OBS was established to address this fragmentation by providing a structured and cumulative resource for identifying, organising, and documenting methodological developments relevant to HTA.

This second annual update extends the observatory in two important respects. First, it brings ongoing EU-funded projects within scope, reflecting that many methodological outputs emerge during a project's lifetime rather than only after it has concluded. Second, it incorporates an inventory of methods guides issued by national HTA bodies and the Member State Coordination Group on HTA (EU HTACG). Together, these additions broaden SUSTAIN-OBS from a repository of research-derived methods into a more comprehensive resource that also captures the methodological guidance shaping HTA practice. They also strengthen the observatory's role as a more current and policy-relevant point of reference for the European HTA methodological landscape.

The review identified 18 EU-funded projects relevant to HTA methods: 13 funded under Horizon Europe, four under the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI), and one under the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI). At the time of writing, 17 of these projects were ongoing, with planned end dates spanning 2026 to 2030. Across the included projects, 164 documents (e.g., project deliverables and publications) were retrieved. Of these, 131 met the predefined inclusion criteria and were taken forward for detailed review. This process yielded 13 methods and tools, which were incorporated into the SUSTAIN-OBS database. The update also incorporated 58 methods guides from 34 HTA bodies across 29 European jurisdictions.

Following this second annual review, the observatory now covers 25 EU-funded projects and catalogues 66 methods and tools. It also includes a dedicated HTA Methods Guides section to house the guidance documents incorporated through this update. In addition, the tool has been migrated from an Excel-based format to an open-access web platform, improving navigation, filtering, and overall usability.

The report concludes by setting out priorities for the next phase of development. These include verifying database entries with method developers and further expanding coverage by identifying relevant methods and tools from international professional bodies. Future work will also promote the use of the platform's submission function so that users can propose new methods for inclusion. Alongside continued monitoring of ongoing and newly initiated projects, a systematic literature review will be undertaken to address methodological needs highlighted by the SUSTAIN Horizon Scanning Tool (SUSTAIN-HS). Finally, the web platform will continue to be refined in response to user feedback.

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1 Introduction

Over the past decade, the European Union (EU) has invested substantially in research to advance health technology assessment (HTA) methodology. These investments have generated a wide range of methods, tools, and frameworks designed to address emerging challenges in HTA. Yet the implementation of these methodological developments in routine HTA practice remains inconsistent and, in many cases, limited.

The reasons underlying this gap between methodological development and practical uptake are not fully understood. Possible explanations include insufficient dissemination beyond individual research projects, implementation barriers within HTA bodies, concerns regarding feasibility in real-world assessment contexts, and misalignment between research outputs and the needs of HTA bodies. Whatever the underlying causes, the result is a fragmented methodological landscape in which valuable methodological advances risk remaining underused or becoming difficult to locate once the projects that produced them conclude.

The SUSTAIN Methods Observatory Tool (SUSTAIN-OBS) was developed as part of the SUSTAIN-HTA Coordination and Support Action to address this challenge. The observatory provides a structured platform for identifying, organising, and documenting innovative methods and tools relevant to HTA, with particular attention to methodological developments emerging from EU-funded research initiatives. These developments are identified and captured through annual reviews conducted within SUSTAIN-HTA.

The first annual overview of HTA methods laid the groundwork for this effort. The report identified and catalogued 53 distinct methods and tools developed through seven EU-funded research projects completed between 2020 and 2024 under Horizon 2020 and the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) (Elayan et al., 2025a). The exercise demonstrated considerable methodological developments relevant to HTA, generated through European research programmes, while also underscoring persistent challenges in the discoverability and accessibility of these methods and tools for the HTA community.

The present report represents the second annual iteration of this work and extends the scope of SUSTAIN-OBS in two important aspects. First, the observatory has been expanded to include ongoing EU-funded research projects under Horizon Europe and the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI). Whereas the first report focused exclusively on completed projects, many methodological contributions from EU-funded initiatives are produced and disseminated during the projects' lifetimes through (interim) deliverables, publications, and technical reports. Incorporating ongoing projects, therefore, allows SUSTAIN-OBS to capture methodological developments as they emerge and provides a more current picture of the evolving HTA methodological landscape.

Second, the present update incorporates a systematic inventory of methods guides issued by national HTA bodies and the Member State Coordination Group on HTA (EU HTACG). This component builds on the work undertaken in Task 1.4, which reviewed methods guides published by European HTA bodies and the EU HTACG (Salih et al., 2025). Integrating these materials adds an important complementary perspective to the observatory by situating methodological developments emerging from research projects alongside the frameworks currently applied in HTA bodies' practice.

Taken together, these additions substantially extend the coverage of SUSTAIN-OBS and represent a further step in its continued development. By identifying recent methodological developments and integrating published methods guides, the observatory continues to serve as a living resource that

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enhances the visibility and accessibility of innovative HTA methods and tools, while also moving towards becoming a cumulative and trusted reference point for the HTA methodological landscape in Europe.

2 Methods

1.1 Ongoing EU-Funded Projects

2.1.1 Identification

The identification of ongoing EU-funded projects followed a multi-stage approach similar to that employed in the first annual review (Elayan et al., 2025a). Consortium members drew on their participation in ongoing research projects and their knowledge of the European HTA methodological landscape to nominate projects currently developing methods or tools relevant to HTA.

This internal identification process was complemented by consultations with members of the SUSTAIN-HTA Expert Forum and Stakeholder Forum during scheduled meetings. During these consultations, forum members were invited to identify additional ongoing EU-funded projects with potential methodological relevance to HTA. This combined approach aimed to ensure broad coverage of relevant research initiatives while reducing the risk of overlooking important projects.

2.1.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria applied to outputs from ongoing EU-funded projects were consistent with those established for completed projects in the first annual report (Elayan et al., 2025a).

Outputs were considered eligible for inclusion if they:

- (a) presented or described a method or tool relevant to HTA;
- (b) were accessible through the EU Funding & Tenders Portal or official project websites; or
- (c) were reported in peer-reviewed publications that included an explicit funding statement linking the publication to the corresponding project.

Outputs were excluded if they reported exclusively on project management, administrative coordination, or topics that lacked methodological relevance to HTA.

2.1.3 Data Extraction

Data extraction for ongoing EU-funded projects followed the same structured protocol established for completed projects in the first annual report (Elayan et al., 2025a). For each project, information was recorded on the project name, funding scheme, starting date, expected completion date, and the project's methodological focus and objectives.

For each identified method or tool, information was extracted on the type of technology to which it is applicable, a description of the method or tool, its type, and supplementary information relevant to its applicability (e.g., geographic and clinical scope). Links to project deliverables, publications, or other outputs documenting the method/tool were also recorded where available.

The classification of identified methods and tools according to the HTA domain and methodological area followed the SUSTAIN-HTA taxonomy developed in Task 1.2 (Elayan et al., 2024a; Elayan et

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al., 2024b). Where necessary, extensions to the taxonomy were introduced to accommodate domains or areas that were not present in the taxonomy at the time of the first report. These extensions will be documented in a forthcoming update to the taxonomy report.

2.2 HTA Methods Guides

HTA methods guides incorporated into SUSTAIN-OBS were drawn from the review conducted in Task 1.4. The review examined methods guides published by the EU HTACG, a purposively selected sample of 12 national HTA methods guides on clinical effectiveness, and all identified national HTA methods guides in Europe relating to cost-effectiveness analysis and other aspects of HTA. Detailed information on the identification and review process is reported elsewhere (Salih et al., 2025). For each document, information recorded included the issuing body, the title of the methods guide, the year of publication, the language, and, where available, a link to the source document.

3 Results

3.1 Ongoing EU-Funded Projects

3.1.1 Projects Identified

A total of 18 EU-funded research projects were identified as contributing to the development of methods and tools relevant to HTA (Table 1). Of these, 13 were funded under Horizon Europe, four under the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI), and one under the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI). At the time of writing, 17 projects remained ongoing, while HI-PRIX had concluded on 31 December 2025. Of the projects still active, nine were scheduled to conclude in 2026, three in 2027, two in 2028, two in 2029, and one in 2030.

Table 1. Ongoing EU-Funded Projects Newly Incorporated into SUSTAIN-OBS

Project	Funding Scheme	Start	End	Status
ASCERTAIN	Horizon Europe	1 Dec 2022	30 Nov 2026	Ongoing
ASSESS-DHT	Horizon Europe	1 Jan 2024	31 Dec 2026	Ongoing
EDiHTA	Horizon Europe	1 Jan 2024	31 Dec 2027	Ongoing
GREG	IHI	1 May 2025	30 Apr 2030	Ongoing
H2O	IMI	1 Oct 2020	31 Mar 2026	Ongoing
HEU-EFS	IHI	1 Oct 2023	30 Sep 2027	Ongoing
HI-PRIX	Horizon Europe	1 Jan 2023	31 Dec 2025	Completed
IDERHA	IHI	1 Apr 2023	31 Mar 2028	Ongoing
INSAFEDARE	Horizon Europe	1 Nov 2023	31 Oct 2026	Ongoing
INVENTS	Horizon Europe	1 Jan 2024	31 Dec 2028	Ongoing
More-EUROPA	Horizon Europe	1 Jan 2023	31 Dec 2027	Ongoing
ONCOVALUE	Horizon Europe	1 Dec 2022	30 Nov 2026	Ongoing
PHASE IV AI	Horizon Europe	1 Oct 2023	30 Sep 2026	Ongoing
REALM	Horizon Europe	1 Jan 2023	31 Dec 2026	Ongoing
Real4Reg	Horizon Europe	1 Jan 2023	31 Dec 2026	Ongoing
REDDIE	Horizon Europe	1 Jan 2023	31 Dec 2026	Ongoing
REPO4EU	Horizon Europe	1 Sep 2022	31 Aug 2029	Ongoing
SYNTHIA	IHI	1 Sep 2024	31 Aug 2029	Ongoing

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The identified projects address a wide range of methodological topics relevant to HTA. Real-world data (RWD) featured prominently, with several projects addressing their generation, use, or appraisal for regulatory and HTA decision-making, including Real4Reg, REALM, REDDIE, More-EUROPA, IDERHA, and GREG. Other projects address the evaluation of digital health technologies and software-based interventions (EDiHTA, ASSESS-DHT, REALM), pricing and reimbursement or affordability frameworks (ASCERTAIN, HI-PRIX), patient-centred outcomes infrastructures (H2O), synthetic data and privacy-preserving data use (SYNTHIA, PHASE IV AI, INSAFEDARE), early feasibility studies for medical devices (HEU-EFS), drug repurposing (REPO4EU), and evidence-generation approaches for rare diseases (INVENTS).

3.1.2 Methods and Tools Identified

Across the 18 projects included in this update, 164 documents (e.g., project deliverables and publications) were retrieved. Of these, 131 met the predefined inclusion criteria and were deemed eligible for further analysis. The analysis identified 13 methods and tools for incorporation into the SUSTAIN-OBS database. All identified outputs originated from five projects: H2O, More-EUROPA, INSAFEDARE, REPO4EU, and HI-PRIX. Table 2 summarises the identified outputs and their originating projects.

Table 2. Methods and Tools Identified from Ongoing EU-Funded Projects

Project	Method / Tool	Type	Description
H2O	Data quality rules for health data assessment	Method	Rules for assessing health data quality across its lifecycle, including completeness, consistency, correctness, and other quality dimensions.
H2O	Core outcome set for multiple myeloma	Tool	Consensus-based core outcome set specifying standardised outcomes for patients with multiple myeloma.
H2O	Core outcome set for inflammatory bowel disease	Tool	Core outcome set including patient-reported outcomes, biomarkers, and case-mix variables for inflammatory bowel disease.
H2O	Core outcome set for lung cancer	Tool	Patient-centred core outcome set including clinical and patient-reported outcomes for lung cancer.
H2O	Core outcome set for metastatic breast cancer	Tool	Core outcome set covering baseline characteristics, clinical variables, health-related quality of life, and adverse events for metastatic breast cancer.
H2O	Core outcome set for diabetes	Tool	Person-centred core outcome set including clinical and patient-reported outcomes for diabetes.
More-EUROPA	Registry identification machine learning tool	Tool	Artificial intelligence-based tool for identifying and assessing health registries suitable for research, regulatory, and HTA purposes.
INSAFEDARE	Data pipeline platform for synthetic data generation	Tool	Modular platform for designing and executing workflows to generate synthetic healthcare datasets.

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Project	Method / Tool	Type	Description
INSAFEDARE	Taxonomy of synthetic healthcare data	Taxonomy	Classification framework defining types of synthetic healthcare data based on data proportion, modality, and transformation.
REPO4EU	SMART Tool	Tool	A tool supporting transparent reporting and justification of modelling choices in health economic decision-analytic models.
REPO4EU	Framework on HTA methods for drug repurposing	Method	Framework identifying challenges in drug repurposing and mapping corresponding HTA methods to address them.
HI-PRIX	Pay for Innovation Observatory	Tool	Online catalogue of pricing and payment schemes for health innovations.
HI-PRIX	PAID 4.0	Tool	Web-based toolkit supporting the incorporation of future unrelated costs in economic evaluations through case-specific cost estimates.

3.2 HTA Methods Guides

A total of 58 methods guides were identified, of which five were issued by the EU HTACG and the remainder by 34 national HTA bodies across 29 European jurisdictions. The full list of HTA bodies whose methods guides are included in the observatory is provided in Table 3.

Table 3. HTA Bodies Contributing Methodological Guides to SUSTAIN-OBS

Country	HTA body
Austria	Austrian Institute for Health Technology Assessment (AIHTA)
Belgium	Belgian Health Care Knowledge Centre (KCE)
Belgium	National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance (RIZIV/INAMI)
Bulgaria	The National Council on Prices and Reimbursement of Medicinal Products (NCPRMP)
Croatia	Croatian Health Insurance Fund (HZZO)
Czechia	State Constitution for The Control of Medicines (SUKL)
Denmark	Danish Medicines Council (DMC)
Denmark	The Danish Healthcare Quality Institute (DHQI)
England	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE)
European Union	Member State Coordination Group on HTA (HTA CG)
Finland	Pharmaceuticals Pricing Board (HILA)
Finland	Finnish Medicines Agency (FIMEA)
France	Haute Autorité Santé (HAS)
Germany	Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG)
Greece	Greek Ministry of Health
Hungary	Nemzeti Népegészségügyi és Gyógyszerészeti Központ (NNGYK)
Ireland	Health Information and Quality Authority (HIQA) / National Centre for Pharmacoeconomics (NCPE)
Italy	Agenzia Italiana del Farmaco (AIFA)
Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia	Multiple institutions*
Lithuania	States Medicines Control Service
Netherlands	National Health Care Institute (ZIN)

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Country	HTA body
Norway	The Norwegian Medical Products Agency (NOMA)
Norway	Nye metoder
Poland	Agency for Health Technology Assessment and Tariff System (AOTMiT)
Portugal	National Authority for Medicament and Health Products (INFARMED)
Scotland	Scottish Medicines Consortium (SMC)
Scotland	Scottish Health Technologies Group (SHTG)
Slovakia	Národný inštitút pre hodnotu a technológie v zdravotníctve (NIHO)
Slovenia	Ministry of Health
Spain	The Spanish Network of Agencies for Health Technology Assessment and Services of the National Health System (RedETS)
Sweden	Dental and Pharmaceutical Benefits Agency (TLV)
Sweden	Statens Beredning For Medicinsk Och Social Utvardering (SBU)
Switzerland	Federal Office for Public Health (FOPH)
Wales	Health Technology Wales (HTW)
Wales	All Wales Medicines Strategy Group (AWMSG)
* The Baltic guideline for economic evaluation of pharmaceuticals was issued in 2002 by the Medicines' Pricing and Reimbursement Agency (Latvia), the Health Insurance Fund and the Ministry of Social Affairs (Estonia), and the Department of Pharmacy under the Ministry of Health (Lithuania).	

3.3 Overview of the updated database

The SUSTAIN-OBS database has been updated to incorporate the additional material identified via this second annual review. Database content has been expanded to include the newly incorporated projects, the newly identified methods and tools, and the methods guides. While the overall structure of the database has been retained, selected structural adjustments have been introduced to accommodate these additions. The structure of the updated database is described below.

Overview of Projects tab: The Overview of Projects tab now includes all 25 EU-funded projects incorporated into SUSTAIN-OBS, comprising eight completed and 17 ongoing projects. Each record includes the project name, funding programme, and a high-level summary. A project status field has also been added to enable users to distinguish between completed and ongoing projects and to filter records accordingly.

Methods Explorer tab (formerly the Repository tab): The Methods Explorer tab remains the principal interface for exploring the methods and tools catalogued in the observatory. The field structure of the tab has been retained, and each record continues to include the project name, funding source, project status, applicable technology type, HTA domain classification, methodological category and type, method or tool description, geographic and clinical scope, and additional information on applicability. The tab's content has been expanded to include all 66 methods and tools identified to date.

Abbreviations tab: The Abbreviations tab has been updated to include additional abbreviations used across the expanded database.

HTA Methods Guides tab: A new tab, HTA Methods Guides, has been added to house the HTA methods guides incorporated into the observatory. Each row in this tab corresponds to a single methods guide and includes fields for the source link, language, and publication year, where

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available. Within the tab, national methods guides are organised by country and issuing HTA body, whereas those published by the EU HTACG are presented separately as EU-level entries.

The updated database is now hosted on the openly accessible web-based SUSTAIN-OBS platform (<https://sustain-hta.shinyapps.io/SUSTAIN-OBS>), replacing the earlier Excel-based version. Migration to a web-based platform enables easier navigation, filtering, and exploration of projects, methods, and guidance materials. Detailed documentation of the platform and its functionalities is provided elsewhere (Elayan et al., 2025b).

4 Discussion

This second annual overview extends the scope of SUSTAIN-OBS in two important respects. First, it expands coverage from completed EU-funded research projects to include ongoing projects, thereby providing an up-to-date account of methodological development in HTA across the EU. Second, it incorporates methods guides published by national HTA bodies and the EU HTACG, adding a practice-oriented perspective to the research-focused mapping undertaken in the first report.

The projects captured in this update reflect a broader methodological scope than those covered in the first annual report. The earlier set centred chiefly on RWD, predictive modelling, health-related quality of life, and costing and resource use. By contrast, the projects identified here extend beyond those areas to include digital health technologies, synthetic data, pricing and reimbursement, drug repurposing, early feasibility studies, and evidence generation for rare diseases. This widening of scope suggests that methodological development relevant to HTA is increasingly being shaped by more complex data environments, evolving evidence needs, and emerging types of health technologies.

The prominence of projects addressing RWD and RWE is particularly notable. Several of the identified projects focus on the generation, use, or appraisal of RWE intended to inform regulatory or HTA decision-making. This points to continued methodological attention to evidence environments in which routine RWD, registries, and linked health and administrative data sources are expected to play a larger role in assessment. The presence of projects on digital health technologies, AI-related applications, and synthetic data further indicates that methodological development is responding to challenges posed by data-intensive and software-based technologies, for which traditional evaluative approaches may require adaptation.

Although 18 projects were identified, only 13 methods and tools had been captured at the time of this update. This disparity reflects the fact that many of these projects remain ongoing, with methodological outputs typically emerging gradually and, in some cases, remaining confidential until project completion. The methods identified at this stage, therefore, provide a provisional account of the broader methodological contribution these projects may ultimately make.

That said, the identified methods already point to several important directions in current methodological developments. One concerns the standardisation of outcomes and patient-centred measurement. The core outcome sets developed within H2O across multiple disease areas reflect continued methodological attention to harmonising outcome selection and measurement across research and care settings. For HTA, this matters because greater consistency in outcome measurement may improve comparability across studies and strengthen the use of patient-relevant outcomes in assessment and appraisal.

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A second area concerns data quality, data infrastructures, and advanced data use. H2O has developed data quality rules for health data assessment, providing a structured approach to evaluating data quality throughout the health data lifecycle, including dimensions such as completeness, consistency, and correctness. More-EUROPA has developed a machine learning-based tool for registry identification to support the identification and assessment of health registries for research, regulatory, and HTA purposes. INSAFEDARE contributes two related outputs: a data pipeline platform for generating synthetic datasets and a taxonomy of synthetic healthcare data based on dimensions such as data proportion, modality, and transformation. Collectively, these outputs address the conditions under which data can be identified, characterised, assessed, and used. Their relevance to HTA lies not only in downstream analysis, but also in the quality and structure of the evidence base on which assessment increasingly depends.

A third area concerns economic evaluation and methodological transparency. REPO4EU has developed the SMART tool to support the systematic reporting and justification of modelling choices in health economic decision-analytic models. HI-PRIX has also produced the PAID 4.0 toolkit, a web-based application that facilitates the incorporation of future unrelated medical and non-medical costs in economic evaluations by generating case-specific cost estimates based on demographic and healthcare expenditure projections.

A fourth area concerns context-specific methodological challenges in HTA. REPO4EU has produced a framework for addressing drug repurposing challenges, identifying 20 key challenges and mapping potential methodological responses, including empirical research, stakeholder consultation, economic evaluation, and uncertainty analysis. HI-PRIX has also developed the Pay-for-Innovation Observatory, an online catalogue of pricing and payment schemes applied or proposed for medicines, medical devices, digital health tools, and combination products. Both outputs point to methodological work directed towards decision contexts in which established HTA approaches may require adaptation.

Overall, the identified methods indicate that current methodological development relevant to HTA spans both core evaluative functions, such as outcome measurement and economic modelling, and enabling functions related to data quality, data discovery, and data infrastructures.

A further contribution of this update is the incorporation of methods guides issued by national European HTA bodies and the EU HTACG. The inclusion of these guides broadens SUSTAIN-OBS from a repository of research-derived methods into a resource that also encompasses methodological frameworks currently used in HTA bodies' practice. Bringing these two sources together provides a more complete account of the HTA methodological landscape in Europe and allows methodological innovation to be considered in relation to the frameworks that currently shape practice. Although the present report does not undertake a formal comparison between research outputs and guidance documents, it lays the groundwork for such analyses in future iterations.

5 Next Steps

SUSTAIN-OBS is intended to function as a living resource that evolves alongside methodological development relevant to HTA. The observatory will therefore continue to be maintained and updated in future iterations to ensure that the database remains current and reflective of emerging methodological work. The activities outlined below represent the next steps in further developing and maintaining the observatory.

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Verification of database content with method developers: The methods and tools currently documented in SUSTAIN-OBS are being verified in consultation with their developers to confirm the accuracy of the information recorded in the database, including descriptions, classifications, and links to source materials. This exercise is carried out through a dedicated verification form circulated to contacts involved in the projects from which these entries originate. As additional methods and tools are identified in forthcoming annual reviews, they will likewise undergo verification to ensure that the accuracy of the database content is maintained as the observatory continues to evolve. In future updates, the verification workflow will be further optimised and integrated directly into the tool to enable a more streamlined, efficient process.

Identification of methods and tools emerging from international professional societies: Work is ongoing to identify methodological developments emerging from international professional organisations, including Cochrane, the Society for Medical Decision Making (SMDM), the International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research (ISPOR), the European Medicines Agency (EMA), and Health Technology Assessment International (HTAi).

Promoting active use of the submission function: A next step is to encourage active use of the existing submission function as a main route for proposing methods and tools for inclusion in SUSTAIN-OBS. Promotion of this feature will proceed through presentations, demonstrations, and stakeholder engagement activities that familiarise users with its role and operation. Regular use of the submission function will support the iterative expansion of the database by complementing the annual review cycles with a continuous inflow of methodological developments. It will also strengthen the positioning of SUSTAIN-OBS as an authoritative venue for disseminating and documenting research advancements, reinforcing the tool's long-term utility and sustainability.

Systematic literature review: A systematic literature review will be undertaken to identify additional methods and tools relevant to HTA that may not be captured through project-based mapping or professional society activities. The review will concentrate on methodological areas highlighted by the SUSTAIN-HTA Horizon Scanning Tool (SUSTAIN-HS) as requiring further development. The resulting findings will be incorporated into SUSTAIN-OBS and reported in the fourth annual overview of HTA methods, planned for 2027.

Continuous update of ongoing projects and inclusion of newly initiated projects: The observatory will continue to monitor the progress of ongoing EU-funded projects and incorporate additional methodological developments as they become available. Newly initiated projects with methodological relevance to HTA will also be added to the database as they are identified.

Continue to refine the tool's functionality in response to feedback: The tool's functionality will continue to be updated based on user and stakeholder feedback gathered through ongoing engagement and use. Future refinements will aim to improve usability, enhance the overall user experience, and ensure the observatory remains responsive to users' evolving needs.

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